

Arnold's cat map secure multiple-layer reversible watermarking

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ABSTRACT

Reversible watermarking is a novel approach to digital copyright protection that allows the embedding of watermarks into digital data using multiple layers while retaining the ability to recover the original content without data loss. This method provides a unique solution for securing digital data while maintaining the integrity and quality of the content. Nonetheless, new challenges have emerged with the increase in attacks on this method, as reversible watermarking methods lack security keys, making it easy to extract and modify hidden data. In this paper, we present a method for multiple-layer reversible watermarking with security keys, with the goal of addressing the challenges posed by attacks and improving data protection within embedded content. The method uses Arnold's cat map to scramble images, and data embedding in predetermined iterations serves as the method's security key. We put the method through its paces with six grayscale images. With this method, the embedding capacity can reach 2.999 bpp across four layers of embedding, while the visual image quality can reach 22.01 dB. The outcomes from this approach are that the security of multiple-layer reversible watermarking can be enhanced while preserving the capacity to embed data in each layer.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In our rapidly evolving digital age, ensuring the security of copyrights and the preservation of digital data integrity have gained increasing significance. One approach used to achieve these goals involves the use of watermark methods, as described in [1], [2]. A watermark, in this context, refers to a symbol or piece of information that is embedded into an image or digital document to establish ownership or validate its authenticity. Watermarking in sensitive images such as military, artwork, and medical images must be approached with great care because of the significance of every piece of information [1]–[6]. One of the methods used is reversible watermarking. Reversible watermarking enables us to embed watermarks into digital data without sacrificing the original information [1]–[10]. In other words, we can add watermarks to an image or digital document without compromising the underlying data and recover the original image without any distortion.

In recent years, reversible watermarking has garnered significant research attention because of its ability to reversibly restore the original image. The difference expansion (DE) method, which Tian [4] invented, is an illustration of straightforward reversible watermarking. This method involves embedding data bits into

the disparities between pairs of pixels. These disparities are partitioned into eight-bit planes, with the data bits embedded in the least significant bit. This approach further amplifies the differences between the pixel pairs. Over the last few years, multiple reversible watermarking methods have been rapidly developed, all rooted in the DE method concept. This development focuses on improving the performance of DE methods, such as embedding capacity, visual quality, and complexity.

Numerous researchers have introduced various methods to enhance image quality. For example, Liu *et al.* [5] introduced the concept of reduced difference expansion (RDE), whereas Yi *et al.* [11] presented the improved reduced difference expansion (IRDE). Both of these methods were successful in improving the image quality. In contrast, Abdullah and Manaf [12] suggested embedding data in smooth regions using the DE method, and Maniriho and Ahmad [13] proposed data embedding in smooth areas using the DE method along with the modulus function. These approaches also improved the image quality, although they reduced the embedding capacity. To increase the embedding capacity, researchers have devised various methods to alter the block sizes used. For instance, Alattar introduced methods [14], [15] using blocks of sizes 1×3 and 2×2 with a pixels being the based point. Hsiao *et al.* [16] employed blocks of size 3×3 , Based on two predetermined thresholds, all blocks are categorized into three groups: smooth, normal, or complex. Complex blocks are excluded from data embedding, whereas a smooth block will carry twice the amount of data as a normal block, Ahmad *et al.* [17] used 2×2 blocks and reduced the difference value of the pixel with the RDE method, Arham *et al.* [3] used 2×2 blocks and reduced the difference value of the pixel with the IRDE method, Al Huti *et al.* [18] employed 4×5 blocks and reduced the difference value with a modified RDE, and Syahlan and Ahmad [2] used 2×2 blocks and reduced the difference value of the pixel with a modified RDE. All of these outcomes demonstrated that this approach expanded the data embedding and resulted in good visual quality. Various alternative reversible data embedding methods based on the DE method have also been introduced in different sources [19]–[31].

The capability for reversible watermarking, which enables data to be restored to its original state, permits the use of layered embedding to enhance the capacity of embedding [23]. The concept of multi-layer embedding using the DE method began with Tian [4], who initially focused on the DE method alone. Subsequently, Lou *et al.* [32] introduced the idea of merging the DE and RDE schemes. Yi *et al.* [11] expanded upon this by introducing a multi-layer embedding approach that combines DE with IRDE. Furthermore, Wang *et al.* [33], Pan *et al.* [34] presented multi-layer embedding techniques that use a histogram shifting scheme. Arham *et al.* [3] introduced a reversible watermarking method that used embedding data with a multiple-layer approach, incorporating both the IRDE and the DE of Quad methods. Lee *et al.* [35] proposed multiple-layer reversible watermarking with an improved method of [3] by expanding the size of the block used according to the scanning strategy. Maniriho *et al.* [1] introduced a novel approach to multi-layer reversible watermarking for medical images. Their proposal involves a fresh, uncomplicated data embedding (DE) method and a block-based reversible multiple-layer data hiding method. Mehbodniya *et al.* [24] proposed multiple-layer reversible watermarking based on DE using multiple-layer thresholding. The multiple-level thresholding technique uses a combination of the smile mould algorithm (SMA) and the Otsu evaluation function.

Nevertheless, security concerns persist as a consideration in these reversible data embedding methods. The absence of a security key implies that unauthorized parties can effortlessly access and alter the secret data if they are familiar with the embedding method. To enhance the security of reversible data embedding, numerous researchers have devised diverse tactics. Wu *et al.* [36] proposed embedding encrypted data in encrypted images at specified locations using an inventive RRBE method that leverages APL. Additionally, Meenpal and Majumder [37] introduced a secure method for reversible data embedding, employing the DE technique within the integer wavelet transform (IWT) domain to embed data into low-frequency blocks of an image. Moreover, several other researchers, cited in [38]–[41], have also put forward secure approaches for reversible data embedding, involving the integration of encrypted data into images using histogram shifting methodologies. These aforementioned strategies typically entail the use of encryption for the confidential data to be embedded, thereby reinforcing the security level within the reversible data embedding process.

Nonetheless, reversible watermarking methods do exhibit vulnerabilities, particularly regarding security. In this study, we propose a novel approach to secure multiple-layer reversible watermarking using Arnold's cat map as the underlying algorithm. Our objective is to elucidate how this strategy seeks to bolster security in the process of embedding watermarks across diverse layers, thereby introducing complexity for unauthorized entities attempting to access or manipulate the embedded watermark.

This paper is structured into four main sections. In the first section, we introduce the research context and provide an overview of prior studies associated with the difference expansion method. In section 2 provides an extensive elucidation of our proposed approach, covering the embedding process, extraction, and intricacies of the method computations. In section 3 is dedicated to showcasing the experimental outcomes and comparing them with those of the previous method. Finally, section 4 concludes this work.

2. METHOD

This method was proposed to improve the security of embedded data using a secret key in multiple-layer reversible watermarking, particularly those presented by earlier researchers [3]. Secret key used for image obfuscation using arnold's cat map algorithm. The primary contribution of this study lies in enhancing the efficacy of securely embedding data within an image by implementing a secret key for image obfuscation, which involves the utilization of arnold's cat map algorithm.

2.1. Data embedding step

The description below outlines a seven-step embedding process:

Step 1: Select the secret key k to represent the iterations of the arnold cat map for the number of data embedding layers. These iterations k_n should be sequentially defined, starting from 1 and extending until they reach iteration T . The value of T signifies the iteration period of arnold's cat map, and T is less than $3N$, with N representing the images dimensions in an $N \times N$ format. As illustrated, the secret key $k = (5, 25, 56, 95)$ is used for 4 layers of embedding, where $T = 384$, and the image size is $N = 128$.

Step 2: The host image is scrambled using arnold's cat map with the secret key k . This process involves generating new coordinates (x', y') by transforming the existing coordinates (x, y) within an $N \times N$ -sized image. The iteration process is defined by (1). Data embedding occurs at each iteration k_n .

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{i+1} \\ y_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & b \\ c & bc + 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{bmatrix} \text{ mod } (N) \quad (1)$$

The coordinates (x_i, y_i) signify the positions of pixels in the image that change to (x_{i+1}, y_{i+1}) after the i -th iteration. In this context, b and c represent positive integers. Preserving the transformation within the same image area necessitates the determinant of the matrix $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & b \\ c & bc + 1 \end{bmatrix}$ to be equal to 1, indicating that the matrix conserves the area. Arnold's cat map ensures a unique mapping from each pixel to a new pixel position, establishing a one-to-one correspondence. The iteration of arnold's cat map is repeated m times, yielding a different random image with each iteration. The values of b , c , and m , signifying the number of rotations in arnold's cat map, can serve as the secret key. The process involves shifting the image in the y -direction, followed by a shift in the x -direction during each iteration. However, the results might extend beyond the image area; thus, all outcomes are taken modulo N to ensure they remain within the image area, thereby preserving the area. The secret key involves data embedding at different layers during different iterations.

Step 3: During each predetermined iteration, with the aid of the secret key k_n , the image is divided into 2×2 blocks. Subsequently, a pixel vector is generated for each block within each layer to compute the differences between consecutive pixels, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The proposed block of pixels with a base point is (p_0)

Pixels p_0 serves as the reference point, as depicted in Figure 1. This reference point allows us to create vectors $d = (d_1, d_2, d_3)$ which represent the difference values of the vector $p = (p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3)$ and can be expressed as (2).

$$\begin{cases} d_1 = p_1 - p_0 \\ d_2 = p_2 - p_1 \\ d_3 = p_3 - p_2 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Step 4: After completing the calculation of the pixel block pair differences to reduce the distortion of the difference values, (3) is employed, where h is computed using (4). The reduction of the difference value was performed if $(-1 > d_i > 1)$ then the location map $(LM_{d_i}) = (0, 1)$ and if $(-1 \leq d_i \leq 1)$ then the location map $(LM_{d_i}) = (-1)$ show in (5). In the extraction phase, the location map (LM) is used to recover the original difference value from the original pixels of the host image.

$$d'_i = \begin{cases} d_i - 2^{\log_2|d_i|-1}, & \text{if } 2 \times 2^{h-1} \leq d_i \leq 3 \times 2^{h-1} - 1 \\ d_i - 2^{\log_2|d_i|}, & \text{if } 3 \times 2^{h-1} \leq d_i \leq 4 \times 2^{h-1} - 1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$h = \lfloor \log_2 |v_i| \rfloor \quad (4)$$

$$LM_{d_i} = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{if } -1 > d_i > 1 \\ 0, & \text{if } 2 \times 2^{h-1} \leq d_i \leq 3 \times 2^{h-1} - 1 \\ 1, & \text{if } 3 \times 2^{h-1} \leq d_i \leq 4 \times 2^{h-1} - 1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Step 5: To embed a data bit b_i , there are two methods are available, either through (6) or (7). Blocks of pixels that employ (6) to embed data are labelled as expandable and location map $(LM_b) = 1$. In cases where using (6) results in overflow or underflow, the reduction of the difference value was cancelled, and the embedding process was switched to (7) and then labelled as changeable and location map $(LM_b) = 0$. Additionally, blocks are c as unchangeable if they do not fall into the second category and embedding data is not performed then location map $(LM_b) = -1$.

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{d}_1 = 2 \times d'_1 + b_i \\ \tilde{d}_2 = 2 \times d'_2 + b_{i+1} \\ \tilde{d}_3 = 2 \times d'_3 + b_{i+2} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{cases} d'_1 = 2 \times \lfloor \frac{d_1}{2} \rfloor + b_i \\ d'_2 = 2 \times \lfloor \frac{d_2}{2} \rfloor + b_{i+1} \\ d'_3 = 2 \times \lfloor \frac{d_3}{2} \rfloor + b_{i+2} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Each block of pixel has the embedding location map $LM = (LM_1, LM_2, LM_3, LM_4)$, where LM_1 are located to LM_b is categories of the block pixel in expandable, changeable, or non-changeable, and $LM_2, LM_3,$ and LM_4 are located to LM_{d_i} is identify the difference value of the pixel $d = (d_1, d_2, d_3)$ on the block has been reduced. In the case location map $(LM_1) = 0, LM_2, LM_3,$ and LM_4 is set to 1 if the difference value of the pixel $d = (d_1, d_2, d_3)$ is odd, and if the difference value of the pixel $d = (d_1, d_2, d_3)$ is even, then $LM_2, LM_3,$ and LM_4 is set to 0.

Step 6: Following the completion of the embedding process, the next step involves creating a new pixel p'_0 as outlined in (8).

$$\begin{cases} p'_0 = p_0 \\ p'_1 = \tilde{d}_1 + p_0 \\ p'_2 = \tilde{d}_2 + p_1 \\ p'_2 = \tilde{d}_2 + p_2 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In Table 1, we present an illustration showing steps 3 to 6 of how data are hidden in a scrambled image. We illustrate the embedded data.

Table 1. Illustration of the data embedding and extraction

Embedding	Extraction
<p>Step 3: Assume that we have a block of quad of grayscale values, denoted as $p = (112, 125, 149, 157)$, and we compute the difference value, d, using (3).</p> $d_1 = 125 - 112 = 13$ $d_2 = 149 - 125 = 24$ $d_3 = 157 - 149 = 8$ $d = (13, 24, 8)$ <p>Step 4: reduce d using (7)</p> $h = \lfloor \log_2 13 \rfloor = 3 \text{ then, } 3 \times 2^{3-1} \leq 13 \leq 4 \times 2^{3-1} - 1$ $d'_1 = 13 - 2^{\log_2 13 } = 13 - 2^3 = 13 - 8 = 5$ $LM_2 = 1$ $h = \lfloor \log_2 24 \rfloor = 4 \text{ then, } 3 \times 2^{3-1} \leq 24 \leq 4 \times 2^{3-1} - 1$ $d'_2 = 24 - 2^{\log_2 24 } = 24 - 2^4 = 24 - 16 = 8$ $LM_3 = 1$ $h = \lfloor \log_2 8 \rfloor = 3 \text{ then, } 2 \times 2^{3-1} \leq 8 \leq 3 \times 2^{3-1} - 1$ $d'_3 = 8 - 2^{\log_2 8 - 1} = 8 - 2^{3-1} = 8 - 4 = 4$ $LM_4 = 0$ $d' = (5, 8, 4)$ <p>Step 5: Consider that we possess confidential data $b = (101)_2$</p> $\tilde{d}_1 = 2 \times 5 + 1 = 11$ $\tilde{d}_2 = 2 \times 8 + 0 = 16$ $\tilde{d}_3 = 2 \times 4 + 1 = 9$ $\tilde{d} = (11, 16, 9)$ <p>Step 6: Create a new pixel using (12)</p> $p'_0 = p_0 = 112$ $p'_1 = \tilde{d}_1 + p_0 = 11 + 112 = 123$ $p'_2 = \tilde{d}_2 + p_1 = 16 + 125 = 141$ $p'_3 = \tilde{d}_3 + p_2 = 9 + 149 = 158$ $LM_1 = 1$ $p' = (112, 123, 141, 158)$ $LM = (1110)$	<p>Steps 2 and 3: Assuming we have a block of quad of grayscale values, denoted as $p' = (112, 123, 141, 158)$ and $LM = (1110)$, we compute the difference value, \tilde{d}, using (3).</p> $\tilde{d}_1 = 123 - 112 = 11$ $b_1 = LSB(\tilde{d}_1) = LSB(11) = 1$ $d'_1 = \left\lfloor \frac{\tilde{d}_1}{2} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{11}{2} \right\rfloor = 5$ $LM_2 = 1$ $d_1 = d'_1 + 2^{\log_2 d'_1 + 1} = 5 + 8 = 13$ $p_1 = 13 + 112 = 125$ $\tilde{d}_2 = 141 - 125 = 16$ $b_2 = LSB(\tilde{d}_2) = LSB(16) = 0$ $d'_2 = \left\lfloor \frac{\tilde{d}_2}{2} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{16}{2} \right\rfloor = 8$ $LM_3 = 1$ $d_2 = d'_2 + 2^{\log_2 d'_2 + 1} = 8 + 16 = 24$ $p_2 = 24 + 125 = 149$ $\tilde{d}_3 = 158 - 149 = 9$ $b_3 = LSB(\tilde{d}_3) = LSB(9) = 1$ $d'_3 = \left\lfloor \frac{\tilde{d}_3}{2} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{9}{2} \right\rfloor = 4$ $LM_4 = 0$ $d_3 = d'_3 + 2^{\log_2 d'_3 } = 4 + 4 = 8$ $p_3 = 8 + 149 = 157$ $p' = (112, 125, 149, 157)$

2.2. Data extraction step

The extraction process is executed in the following step to retrieve the embedded data:

Step 1: The extraction process is performed as in the embedding stage, with the distinction that data retrieval starts from the last layer. Using the same secret key k as in the embedding process, the watermark image is scrambled using arnold's cat map algorithm using (9), employing the secret key k_n .

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & b \\ c & bc + 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{i+1} \\ y_{i+1} \end{bmatrix} \bmod (N) \quad (9)$$

Step 2: The scrambled watermark in iteration k_n is divided into 2×2 pixel blocks, transformed into vector p' , and the pixel block pair differences \tilde{d} is performed using (3). Uses the LM to uncover hidden data from the LSB differences \tilde{d} where value of LM_b is not -1 . If location map LM_b is 1, use the location map LM_{d_i} restores the image to its original appearance using (10), and if location map LM_b is 0, use (11).

$$d_i = \begin{cases} d'_i + 2^{\log_2 |d'_i| + 1}, & \text{if } LM_{d_i} = 1 \\ d'_i + 2^{\log_2 |d'_i|}, & \text{if } LM_{d_i} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$d_i = \begin{cases} 2 \times \left\lfloor \frac{d'_i}{2} \right\rfloor + 1, & \text{if } LM_{d_i} = 1 \\ 2 \times \left\lfloor \frac{d'_i}{2} \right\rfloor, & \text{if } LM_{d_i} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Step 3: To reconstruct the initial image, we apply (12) as:

$$\begin{cases} p_0 = p_0 \\ p_1 = d_1 + p_0 \\ p_2 = d_2 + p_1 \\ p_3 = d_3 + p_2 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

In Table 1, we present an illustration showing steps 2 and 3 of how data is extracted in a scrambled image.

Step 4: Extract the data and recovery image performed up to the initial iteration. Once all procedures are completed, the image will be restored to its original form.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we conduct a comprehensive evaluation to assess the performance, payload capacity, and imperceptibility of the proposed method compared with that of the existing method [3]. In embedding data not use threshold of difference value. We conducted extensive simulations using six grayscale image variations in Figure 2. Figure 2(a) lena, Figure 2(b) baboon, Figure 2(c) barbara, Figure 2(d) airplane, Figure 2(e) peppers, and Figure 2(f) boat), each with dimensions of 512×512 pixels. Figure 2 provides visual representations of the six test images. The evaluation encompassed the integration of the watermark into the four layers of the image. To compare the similarity between the watermarked image and the original image, we employed two metrics: peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), calculated using (13). PSNR generates higher values to signify greater similarity, whereas mean squared error (MSE) yields smaller values to indicate improved similarity. The secret key $k = (32, 128, 512, 1024)$ is used for 4 layers of embedding, where $T = 1536$, and the image size is $N = 512$.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{m \times n} \sum_i^{m-1} \sum_j^{n-1} |I(i, j) - I'(i, j)|^2 \quad (13)$$

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \frac{255^2}{MSE} \quad (14)$$

Figure 2. The six images used for testing; (a) lena, (b) baboon, (c) barbara, (d) airplane, (e) peppers, and (f) boat

3.1. Performance

The examinations demonstrated that both the embedding and extraction processes operate effectively, allowing the image to be accurately reconstructed to its initial state. The experiments indicated that enhancing the security of multiple-layer reversible watermarking in images can be achieved by first scrambling the image before the embedding process. According to the data in Tables 2 and 3, our method can achieve the maximum data hiding capacity. The results indicate that our approach matches the capacity of the method [3], but it requires more computational time. This is primarily due to the image randomization process using arnold's cat map algorithm, which consumes time proportional to the image resolution. For single-layer embedding, our approach exhibits an average computational time of 767.09, whereas the method [3] has an average computational time of 111.83. In the case of four-layer embedding, our method shows an average computational time of 984.13, whereas method [3] has an average computational time of 406.92.

In Table 2, the average gap in computational time between our method and that of [3] amounts to 655.26. Contrasting outcomes are evident in Table 3, specifically in the case of four-layer embedding, where the average computational time difference between our method and that of [3] is 577.21. This disparity arises from the embedding process occurring during specific iterations within a single randomization iteration period using arnold's cat algorithm.

3.2. Payload (incorporating capacity)

Our test results indicate that in a single layer, as shown in Table 2, our method and method [3] have the same data embedding capacity, both averaging 0.75 bits per pixel (bpp). This embedding capacity can

be achieved without applying the threshold of the pixel difference value. Furthermore, when we consider the average data embedding capacity across all four layers based on Table 3, our method exhibits a slight reduction of approximately 0.0004 bpp compared with the method [3]. This reduction is still manageable, primarily because our proposed method involves an initial randomization of the image before the data embedding process.

Table 2. Comparison of embedding capacities and computational time in a single layer

		Capacity (bits)		Embedding capacity (bpp)		Computational time (second)	
		Method [3]	Our method	Method [3]	Our method	Method [3]	Our method
Lena	512 × 512	196,608	196,608	0.75	0.75	125.31	751.18
Baboon	512 × 512	196,608	196,608	0.75	0.75	101.36	718.61
Barbara	512 × 512	196,608	196,608	0.75	0.75	117.06	876.69
Airplane	512 × 512	196,608	196,608	0.75	0.75	108.25	817.72
Peppers	512 × 512	196,608	196,608	0.75	0.75	109.72	724.08
Boat	512 × 512	196,608	196,608	0.75	0.75	109.28	714.24

Table 3. Comparison of the embedding capacities and PSNR values in the four layers

	Capacity (bits)		Embedding capacity (bpp)		PSNR (dB)		Computational time (second)	
	Method [3]	Our method	Method [3]	Our method	Method [3]	Our method	Method [3]	Our method
Lena	786,432	786,294	3.0000	2.9995	35.96	21.75	366.56	981.61
Baboon	786,432	786,411	3.0000	2.9999	30.02	22.22	429.59	1,004.37
Barbara	786,420	786,279	2.9999	2.9994	30.32	21.47	407.27	1,008.47
Airplane	786,420	786,231	2.9999	2.9992	34.72	22.61	376.74	965.47
Peppers	786,432	786,354	3.0000	2.9997	36.14	21.41	414.04	968.64
Boat	786,411	786,384	2.9999	2.9998	33.37	22.64	447.31	976.21

3.3. Imperceptibility

The test results provide assurance that the image quality remains within acceptable standards following the data embedding process. Table 4 displays the detailed comparison results with the proposed method [3]. On average, in the case of single-layer embedding, the image quality post-embedding attains a commendable 28.25 dB as per the PSNR metric. For the four-layer embedding approach, the average image quality after the embedding process registers at 22.01 dB according to the PSNR.

Among the individual images subjected to single-layer embedding, the boat image stands out with the highest quality, boasting a PSNR of 29.05 dB. Conversely, the lena image exhibited the lowest quality among this group, with a PSNR of 27.54 dB. In the context of four-layer embedding, as shown in Table 3, the boat image emerges as the leader in image quality, recording a PSNR of 22.64 dB, whereas the peppers image again exhibits the lowest quality, with a PSNR of 21.41 dB.

Table 4. Comparison of the PSNR values for single-layer embedding

		PSNR value (dB) in bits per pixel (bpp)						
		0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Lena	Method [3]	55.05	50.44	47.60	45.46	43.94	42.83	41.93
	Our method	36.27	33.26	31.51	30.27	29.30	28.50	27.83
Baboon	Method [3]	41.14	38.44	37.52	37.01	36.55	36.05	35.45
	Our method	37.18	34.20	32.43	31.17	30.20	29.41	28.75
Barbara	Method [3]	49.54	47.00	43.91	40.69	38.33	36.75	35.74
	Our method	36.59	33.57	31.84	30.59	29.64	28.85	28.18
Airplane	Method [3]	52.96	50.73	47.81	43.77	42.05	41.13	40.65
	Our method	37.64	34.65	32.88	31.63	30.66	29.87	29.21
Peppers	Method [3]	49.71	46.90	45.13	43.66	42.95	42.40	41.88
	Our method	36.48	33.44	31.67	30.43	29.46	28.67	28.00
Boat	Method [3]	49.94	45.97	42.98	41.07	39.96	39.51	39.28
	Our method	37.77	34.75	33.03	31.79	30.82	30.03	29.35

According to the comparison results in Tables 3 and 4, the use of Arnold's cat map algorithm for randomization before data embedding has an influence on the image quality following the embedding process. This influence is evident when comparing our approach with a previous method [3]. In the case of single-layer embedding, as shown in Table 4, the average decrease in visual quality was 11.43 dB. The most significant decrease was observed in the Lena image, with an average reduction of 15.76 dB, whereas the smallest decrease was observed in the Baboon image, with an average reduction of 5.55 dB. In the context of four-layer embedding, the average decrease in visual quality was 11.41 dB, with the Lena image experiencing the most substantial reduction at 14.21 dB, whereas the Baboon image exhibited the lowest decrease with an average of 7.80 dB.

4. CONCLUSION

Reversible watermarking is a creative way to protect digital copyrights because it allows watermarks to be added to digital content with multiple-layers without changing the original data. However, despite its utility, this technique is susceptible to attacks because of the absence of security keys in reversible watermarking methods. This study bolsters the security level of multiple-layer reversible watermarking methods by leveraging Arnold's cat map as the foundational algorithm. The proposed approach effectively elevates security in watermark embedding. Through the use of security keys during the embedding process, we adeptly address the vulnerabilities inherent in security-key-lacking reversible watermarking methods while still preserving the capacity to recover the original data. Although our method experiences an increased computational time and reduction in visual quality compared with the previously proposed method, it maintains embedding capacity, ease of implementation, and simplicity. The post-data hiding image quality remains acceptable, as corroborated by the substantial PSNR values achieved. The security of the proposed technique can be further enhanced by encrypting the embedded data. This research can make valuable contributions to safeguarding digital copyrights and preserving data integrity in the upcoming era.

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